

Mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with glycine and 4,6-dimethyl-2-guanidinopyrimidine

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Abstract : Equilibrium study on the mixed-ligand complex formation of the $3d(M^{\text{II}})$ ions ($M = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ and Zn) with glycine ($\text{H}_3\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$, $\text{GlyH}^\pm$) and 4,6-dimethyl-2-guanidinopyrimidine [$\text{H}_2\text{NC}(=\text{NH})\text{NH}\{\text{CN}_2(\text{CCH}_3)_2\text{CH}\}$, Gup] indicate variety of binary and mixed-ligand complexes : $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})^+]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{OH})]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gup})^{2+}]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gup-H})^+]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gup})_2^{2+}]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gup-H})(\text{Gup})^+]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gup-II})_2]$, $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup})^+]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H})]$. With Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} , the mixed-ligand complexes $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup})^+]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H})]$ dominate the pH range of biological relevance, whereas, with Co^{II} and Zn^{II} the $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})^+]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{OH})]$ complexes are the major metal containing species under the same condition. Formation constants of the proton-ligand and metal-ligand complexes at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ in 50% v/v ethanol-water medium (ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were evaluated by computer based pH-metric titration method. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated by analyzing the speciation curves and correlated with the modes of coordination of the ligands.

Keywords : Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , glycine, guanidinopyrimidine, mixed-ligand complex equilibria.

Introduction

Ternary complex formation equilibria play important roles in biological processes¹. Biological metal ions, such as, Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{II} , etc. remain tenaciously bound to the active sites of the enzyme proteins, at the same time, exchange extremely rapidly with the substrates and the products, involving mixed-ligand complexes. Mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of metal ions with amino acids and small peptides as primary ligands and suitably designed secondary ligands provide useful models for mimicking the roles of metal ions at the active sites of the metalloenzymes². Guanidinopyrimidine derivatives, particularly the N-methoxy, N-sulfonyl and N-chlorosulfonyl derivatives are extensively used as herbicides and plant growth regulators³. In view of such medicinal and/or agricultural applications of these materials, it is worthwhile to study the mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of biological metal ions with amino acids, peptides and these pyrimidine derivatives. The present paper describes the results of an equilibrium study on the mixed-ligand complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with the simplest amino acid, glycine ($\text{GlyH}^\pm$)

and 4,6-dimethyl-2-guanidinopyrimidine, hereafter, (guanidinopyrimidine, Gup), (Scheme 1), by pH-metric method (Fig. 1) in 50% v/v ethanol-water medium at ordinary temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Results (Table 1) of such investigation may be useful in elucidating the molecular mechanism of medicinal actions of these derivatives.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

$1 : 1 : 1 M^{\text{II}} : \text{GlyH}_2^+ : \text{GupH}_2^{2+}$ equilibria :

In dilute acidic solution ($\text{pH} \sim 2-3$) both the ligands, glycine ($\text{GlyH}^\pm$, thereafter, GlyH) and 4,6-dimethyl-2-guanidinopyrimidine (Gup) exist in their protonated forms, GlyH_2^+ and GupH_2^{2+} respectively (Scheme 1). With rise

Table 1. Stoichiometry of most possible binary and mixed-ligand M^{II} /glycine/guanidinopyrimidine complexes ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II}) and refined values of the proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants. Temperature : 25 ± 1 °C, ionic strength, I : 0.1 mol dm^{-3} ($NaNO_3$) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium

Sl. no.	Complex species $M_p(Gly)_q(Gup)_r(OH)_s$	p	q	r	s	$\log \beta_{pqrs}$				
						H	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
1.	[GlyH ₂ ⁺]	0	1	0	-2	12.25	-	-	-	-
2.	[GlyH]	0	1	0	-1	9.83	-	-	-	-
3.	[GupH ₂ ²⁺]	0	0	1	-2	12.17	-	-	-	-
4.	[GupH ⁺]	0	0	1	-1	10.08	-	-	-	-
5.	[M(OH) ⁺]	1	0	0	1	-	-8.23	-8.10	-6.29	-7.89
6.	[M(OH) ₂]	1	0	0	2	-	-17.83	-16.87	-13.05	-14.92
7.	[M(Gly) ⁺]	1	1	0	0	-	4.86	5.96	8.53	6.10
8.	[M(Gly)(OH)]	1	1	0	1	-	-2.51	-0.34	1.50	-0.01
9.	[M(Gly) ₂]	1	2	0	0	-	8.84	11.23	16.13	9.98
10.	[M(Gly) ₃ ⁻]	1	3	0	0	-	11.40	13.69	-	-
11.	[M(Gup) ²⁺]	1	0	1	0	-	3.24	5.35	7.61	4.78
12.	[M(Gup-H) ⁺]	1	0	1	1	-	-3.89	-2.46	1.66	-2.45
13.	[M(Gup) ₂ ²⁺]	1	0	2	0	-	5.68	9.12	13.51	5.61
14.	[M(Gup)(Gup-H) ⁺]	1	0	2	1	-	-2.50	2.29	5.55	-2.84
15.	[M(Gup-H) ₂]	1	0	2	2	-	-11.11	-6.59	-3.08	-11.12
16.	[M(Gly)(Gup) ⁺]	1	1	1	0	-	7.62	10.91	15.52	10.53
17.	[M(Gly)(Gup-H)]	1	1	1	1	-	-0.15	6.14	7.05	2.60
	$\Delta \log K_M$ (16)					-	-0.48	-0.40	-0.62	-0.35

Limits of error (σ) : ± 0.02 in log scale.

Fig. 1. Representative pH titration curves of ternary 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : Gup : GlyH systems : ($M = \text{mol dm}^{-3}$); 1, 0.005 (M) HNO_3 ; 2, (1) + 0.001 (M) $GupH_2^{2+}$; 3, (1) + 0.001 (M) H_2Gly^+ ; 4, (2) + 0.001 (M) Cu^{II} ; 5, (3) + 0.001 (M) Cu^{II} ; 6, (5) + 0.001 (M) $GupH_2^{2+}$; initial volume = 0.025 dm^3 , titrant = 0.1 (M) NaOH , ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ (M) NaNO}_3$.

of pH, both the ligand cations undergo stepwise deprotonation. $GlyH_2^+$ loses its $-COOH$ and $-NH_3^+$ pro-

tons in successive steps in the pH ranges 2-3 ($pK_{COOH}^H \sim 2.42$) and 9-10 ($pK_{NH_3}^H \sim 9.83$). The two ring N-atoms 1N and 3N in Gup are structurally equivalent and weakly basic due to resonance in the hetero aromatic π -system. Naturally, deprotonation of $GupH_2^{2+}$ involves stepwise release of the pyrimidinium proton, (either $^1NH^+$ or $^3NH^+$), in the first step ($pK_{H_2}^H \sim 2.09$), followed by deprotonation of the guanidinium proton ($pK_{H_1}^H \sim 10.08$) in the second step.

Complex formation with Cu^{2+} in the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary $Cu^{II} : GlyH_2^+ : GupH_2^{2+}$ system starts around pH 3. As the speciation curves (Fig. 2) imply, the major ($\sim 70\%$) complex species occurring in the pH range 3-6 is the binary complex, $[Cu(Gly)(aq)^+]$ (7) with a minor amount ($\sim 15\%$) of $[Cu(Gup)(aq)^{2+}]$ (11).

As the pH is increased above 6, both (7) and (11) disappear, with simultaneous appearance of the mixed-ligand complexes, $[Cu(Gly)(Gup)^+]$ (16) and Gup-deprotonated $[Cu(Gly)(Gup-H)]$ (17), along with the ternary hydroxo complexes, $[Cu(Gly)(OH)]$ (8), $[Cu(Gup)(OH)]$ (12a), or, $[Cu(Gup-H)^+(aq)]$ (12b), suggesting the existence of a composite equilibria (Scheme 2).

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : GlyH, (b) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : Gup and (c) 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : GlyH : Gup systems : 1, GlyH_2^+ ; 2, GlyH; 3, GupH_2^{2+} ; 4, GupH^+ ; 5, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$; 6, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$; 7, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})^+$; 8, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{OH})$; 11, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gup})^+$; 12, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gup-H})^+$; 16, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup})^+$; 17, $\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H})$; FB1 = Free Gly⁻, FB2 = Free Gup, FM = Free Cu^{II} .

The glycinate anion ($\text{H}_2\text{NCH}_2\text{COO}^-$, Gly⁻) provides bidentate (O⁻, N) chelation to metal ions using its caboxylate O-atom and amino N-atom⁴. Gup provides (N, N) bidentate chelation⁵ using its guanidine N-atom (NH_3^+ group) with deprotonation and a ring N-atom (either ¹N or ³N) (Scheme 3), which is further supported by the close agreement between the stability constants of $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gup})^{2+}(\text{aq})]$ (11) complex and that of the Cu^{II} complex of analogous ligand, 2-(2'-aminoethyl)pyridine^{6,7}, which also provides (N, N) bidentate chelation using an

Scheme 2

amino N-atom (NH_3^+) and a pyridine N-atom, forming a six membered chelate ring, similar to those of $[\text{M}^{\text{II}}(\text{Gup})(\text{aq})^{2+}]$ complexes.

The Cu^{II} (d^9) ion in the binary complexes (7) and (11) tends to take up adequate number of solvent molecules (more likely H_2O molecules, due to greater polarity) to achieve its preferred square planar geometry. The resulting square planar complexes, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+]$ (7) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gup})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]$ (11), undergo deprotonation above $\text{pH} \sim 6$. While (7) loses a proton only from a coordinated H_2O molecule, (11) may undergo deprotonation in more than one ways, viz. deprotonation of a coordinated H_2O ligand, like (7), producing $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gup})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+]$ (12a), as well as deprotonation of the imino (=NH) group through a structural equilibria, (Scheme 3), producing the Gup-deprotonated complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gup-H})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+]$ (12b).

Thus, the binary complex (11) may be described by two tautomeric structures (11a) and (11b), and its deprotonation product may be either (12a) or (12b) or both (Scheme 3). Consequently the ternary complex (16) may be also described by two tautomeric structures (16a) and (16b), in both of which Cu^{II} achieves a square planar $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{O}^-, \text{N})(\text{N}, \text{N})]$ geometry (Scheme 4).

Axially coordinated H_2O molecule, if any, is very weakly bound and is less likely to undergo metal promoted deprotonation. Therefore, deprotonation of the mixed-ligand complex (16) certainly involves loss of a proton from the coordinated imino (=NH) group of the

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Gup ligand. The resulting complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H})]$ (17), being electro neutral, possibly precipitates at the end of titration.

In conformity with the speciation curves (Figs. 3-5), mixed-ligand complex equilibria in 1 : 1 : 1 ternary M^{II} : GlyH : Gup systems, where, $\text{M}^{\text{II}} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II} , may be described according to Scheme 5.

The overall formation constants (β_{pqrs} , eq. (2a)) of the mixed-ligand complexes $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup})]$ (16) are found to be in the Irving-Williams order⁸ : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and the reproportionation constant, expressed as $\Delta \log K_M$ values² (Table 1), where,

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log \beta_{1110} - \log \beta_{1100} - \log \beta_{1010} \quad (1)$$

indicate favoured formation of these mixed-ligand complexes over the corresponding binary ones.

Like the ternary Cu^{II} -GlyH-Gup system, the guanidinopyrimidine deprotonated mixed-ligand Ni^{II} complex, $(\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H}))$ (17) is the dominant Ni^{II} containing species above pH 7 (Fig. 3) in the 1 : 1 : 1 Ni^{II} : GlyH : Gup system. On the other hand, the correspond-

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 Ni^{II} : GlyH, (b) 1 : 1 Ni^{II} : Gup and (c) 1 : 1 : 1 Ni^{II} : GlyH : Gup systems : 1, GlyH_2^+ ; 2, GlyH; 3, GupH_2^{2+} ; 4, GupH^+ ; 5, Ni(OH)^+ ; 6, Ni(OH)_2 ; 7, Ni(Gly)^+ ; 8, Ni(Gly)(OH) ; 11, Ni(Gup)^{2+} ; 12, Ni(Gup-H)^+ ; 16, Ni(Gly)(Gup)^+ ; 17, Ni(Gly)(Gup-H) ; FB1 = Free Gly^- , FB2 = Free Gup, FM = Free Ni^{II} .

ing systems with Co^{II} and Zn^{II} (Figs. 4, 5 respectively) are dominated by the ternary hydroxo complexes, $[\text{M}(\text{Gly})(\text{OH})]$ (8). While $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{Gly})(\text{Gup-H})]$ (17) is formed above pH 6 and makes $\sim 100\%$ of total Ni^{II} around pH 10, the corresponding complexes with Co^{II} and Zn^{II} occur only above pH 8 and their concentrations do not exceed 40% and 10% respectively.

Fig. 4. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 Co^{II} : GlyH, (b) 1 : 1 Co^{II} : Gup and (c) 1 : 1 : 1 Co^{II} : GlyH : Gup systems : 1, GlyH_2^+ ; 2, GlyH; 3, GupH_2^{2+} ; 4, GupH^+ ; 5, Co(OH)^+ ; 6, Co(OH)_2 ; 7, Co(Gly)^+ ; 8, Co(Gly)(OH) ; 11, Co(Gup)^{2+} ; 12, Co(Gup-H)^+ ; 16, Co(Gly)(Gup)^+ ; 17, Co(Gly)(Gup-H) ; FB1 = Free Gly^- , FB2 = Free Gup, FM = Free Co^{II} .

Experimental

Materials and methods :

4,6-Dimethyl-2-guanidinopyrimidine (Gup) was prepared following literature procedure⁵ and purified by recrystallization from hot water. Its purity was tested from elemental analysis and its structure was confirmed from IR spectra and single crystal X-ray diffraction measure-

homometallic mixed-ligand complex species, M_p(Gly)_q(Gup)_r(OH)_s could be defined according to⁹ :

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[\text{M}_p(\text{Gly})_q(\text{Gup})_r(\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{M}]^p[\text{Gly}]^q[\text{Gup}]^r[\text{OH}]^s} \quad (2a)$$

The stoichiometric numbers *p*, *q* and *r* might be positive integers or zero, *s* would be a negative integer for a protonated species, like (GlyH₂[±])⁺, GupH⁺; zero for a normal species, like [M(Gly)⁺], [M(Gup)²⁺], [M(Gly)(Gup)⁺] and positive for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species, like [M(OH)⁺], [M(Gly)(OH)], [M(Gup-H)⁺], [M(Gly)(Gup-H)] *etc.* Charges are omitted for simplicity.

Ionic product (pK_w) of water at the experimental temperature and activity coefficient of H⁺ ion at experimental ionic strength were obtained from literature¹³⁻¹⁵. Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion corresponding to the pH-meter readings were obtained by usual procedure¹⁴ incorporating corrections for the use of mixed solvent¹⁶.

Preliminary values of β₁₁₀₀ of the [M^{II}(Gly)⁺] complexes, obtained from literature¹², were subjected to computer refinement using the SCOGS program⁹ with the pH titration data of the 1 : 1, 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 M^{II} : glycine mixtures and the values corresponding to the minimum standard deviations were accepted. Other β_{pqrs} values (β₁₀₁₀, β₁₁₁₀, β₁₁₁₁, β₁₀₂₀, β₁₂₀₀, β₁₃₀₀, *etc.*), were obtained as computer output. The formation constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values (Table 1) corresponding to the minimum standard deviations (σ, Table 1) were accepted and the same were used to calculate the speciation of the complexes (Figs. 2-5).

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